

Kurd

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Religious Group, Shafi'i, Sunni, Shiite/Shi'a

The Kurds inhabit an area known as Kurdistan, which roughly includes the Zagros and Taurus mountain ranges, and lies along the borders of Turkey, Iraq, Iran, and Syria. Traditionally, the Kurds were nomadic pastoralists or settled agriculturalists, but now mainly live in settled agricultural communities with livestock. The Kurds are predominantly orthodox Sunni Muslims of the Shafi school, however, some tribes are Shiite (Busby, 1996). This entry focuses on the orthodox Sunni Muslim Kurds living in the town and vicinity of Rowanduz, Iraq, ca. 1950. The Kurdish religious beliefs are interwoven through many spheres of life. The religious group is coterminous with the society in the sense that the Kurds are not an autonomous political group, as, "the society is politically integrated with others in a pluralistic state within which it enjoys theoretically equal status (Column 1, Tuden and Marshall, 1972)." Therefore, religion is coterminous with Kurdish society aside from the polity, which is integrated with the Iraq government.

Date Range: 1926 CE - 1955 CE

Region: Kurdistan

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Iraq, Middle East

Town and vicinity of Rowanduz, Iraq ca. 1951

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma11-004>
- Source 1 Description: Hansen, H. H. (1961). Kurdish Woman's Life: Field Research In A Muslim Society, Iraq. Copenhagen Ethnographic Museum Record. Kobenhavn: Nationalmuseet.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma11-008>
- Source 2 Description: Leach, E. R. (1940). Social And Economic Organisation Of The Rowanduz Kurds. Monographs On Social Anthropology. London: London School of Economic and Political Science.
- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma11-002>

- Source 1 Description: Masters, W. M. (1953). Rowanduz: A Kurdish Administrative And Mercantile Center. [S.L.]: [s.n.].
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma11-000>
- Source 2 Description: Busby, Annette. 1996. "Culture Summary: Kurds." New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.
- Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ma11-007>
- Source 3 Description: Barth, F. (1953). Principles Of Social Organization In Southern Kurdistan. Bulletin. Oslo: Brodrene Jorgensen A/S.

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "The sacred book of the Muslim ('one who submits'), the adherent of Islam, is the Quran ('recitation' from the command of its messenger to Muhammad, iqra , 'recite!')..." (Masters, 1953:290).

Are they written:

– Yes

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: "...the revelation of God vouchsafed through the Angel Gabriel to Muhammad..." (Masters, 1953:290).

Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: "...the revelation of God vouchsafed through the Angel Gabriel to Muhammad..." (Masters, 1953:290).

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Kurds are bordered in the north, in the Caucasus, by the Christian Georgians and Muslim Circassians (Masters, 1953:1). Muslims make up the majority of the Iraqi population, but minority groups (including Jews and Christians) are also present (Masters, 1953:166).

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "In central and northern Iraq the Sunna [Muslim faith] is represented by most of the Arab

groups, the Kurds, the Turks, and the Turkomans. The conflict between the two [the Sunna and the Shi'ah], often with violent political expressions, is much the same as that between Catholic and Protestant in Germany, although there is little analogy in the type of religious content" (Masters, 1953:169).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– I don't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– I don't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649 (Frequency of Internal Warfare-resolved rating) indicates that "internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years." Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654 (Pacification) indicates that the Kurds are "not completely pacified: some indication that warfare has decreased because of pacification attempts." (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650 (Frequency of External Warfare-resolved rating) indicates that "external warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years." Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654 (Pacification) indicates that the Kurds are "not completely pacified: some indication that warfare has decreased because of pacification attempts." (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: "The great mosque, Jama'a al-Kabir, in Rowanduz is a large, square building of rubble on the central square of the bazar or mercantile area, its rear wall facing the qibla, the direction of Mecca, to which prayer is addressed" (Masters, 1953:294).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2.5

Notes: "The building on its front is raised about six feet above the square and one reaches its porch by a series of roughly out stone stairs" (Masters, 1953:294).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 3750

Notes: "The town of Rowanduz, as has been noted, has a population of some 5,000 persons..." (Masters, 1953:55), and the Islamic Kurds make up the majority (ibid, 166). If about 75% of the population belongs to the Kurdish group, then the population is about 3750.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Tombs and mosques are present.

Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Saints' graves are also places of worship (see Hansen, 1961:159).

Temples:

– Yes

Notes: "The great mosque, Jama'a al-Kabir , in Rowanduz is a large, square building of rubble on the central square of the bazar or mercantile area, its rear wall facing the qibla , the direction of Mecca, to which prayer is addressed" (Masters, 1953:294).

Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: "In Arabic the word masjid simply signifies a place of prayer. The essential constituents are an open courtyard where the faithful may assemble and a place for ritual ablutions. Historically the covered courtyards, the domes and the minarets are later accretions to the simpler form. In the cool of the hills the open courtyard has been maintained. In most of the villages the mosque is simple paved courtyard of slatestone, surrounded by stone seats with a spring or a fountain in the middle. The slatestone courtyard has the same sanctity as the floor of an ordinary mosque and the visitor must remove his shoes before stepping onto the stone" (Leach, 1940:59).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 75

Notes: Of the inhabitants, 75% are estimated to belong to the Kurdish group, with the remaining 25% belonging to other faiths such as Judaism or Christianity. The Kurds of Rowanduz are all Muslim (Masters, 1953:290).

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 757 (Political and Religious Differentiation) indicates that political and religious leaders are distinct (Ross, 1983; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, the principal ethnographic source does not indicate the religion having explicit, official political support (Masters, 1953).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "It is commonly said that Islam has no priesthood, but at least one author has written an entire volume to disprove this thesis. The functions of the mulla in Rowanduz serve to support the latter view, for they are extremely similar to those of a Christian divine" (Masters, 1953:297). "...the Muslim clergy, the mullas of the Sunnites and the imams of the Shiites..." (Masters, 1953:176).

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: "On the other hand, they [the mullas] are not formally ordained, nor are they subordinate to any higher authority, although they may, if they choose, be attentive to such figures as, say, the Shaykh of Islam in Egypt or the Mufti of Jerusalem. There were three mullas in Rowanduz in 1951, of whom the unofficial leader was Mulla 'Abd al-Karim Effendi, in charge of the great mosque and the control of awqaf" (Masters, 1953:297).

Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: "There is no standard pattern for achieving the priestly office. In Kurdish Iraq a youth who has chosen this as a career simply starts to study with some mulla who already has a position, and, when judged to have shown proficiency, will begin to be supported by the mosque. Others may study at the mosque-schools in Baghdad, Damascus, or other cities, or even seek the famous Mosque of al-Azhar in Cairo. In the first case, the student can ultimately assist and replace his teacher, or the latter may find him a congregation of his own, for there is an exchange of information of this type between the religious leaders of a given locale" (Masters, 1953:297).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: "Another requirement is the duty of pilgrimage to Mecca at least once during the believer's lifetime" (Masters, 1953:303).

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: See Masters, 1953, page 303 for a detailed description of pilgrimage to Mecca.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

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↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

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Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

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Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

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Size and Structure

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Scripture

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Notes: "The sacred book of the Muslim ('one who submits'), the adherent of Islam, is the Quran ('recitation' from the command of its messenger to Muhammad, iqra , 'recite!')..." (Masters, 1953:290).

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: "...the revelation of God vouchsafed through the Angel Gabriel to Muhammad..." (Masters, 1953:290).

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: "...the revelation of God vouchsafed through the Angel Gabriel to Muhammad..." (Masters, 1953:290).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

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Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: "Another requirement is the duty of pilgrimage to Mecca at least once during the believer's lifetime" (Masters, 1953:303).

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: See Masters, 1953, page 303 for a detailed description of pilgrimage to Mecca.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information regarding beliefs about the afterlife

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238 indicates that "a high god is present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, supporting ethnographic information provides evidence for God as an agent of supernatural punishment (Masters, 1953:210). No further information on the nature of supernatural monitoring is available.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Two demands of etiquette, although they may occasionally be observed in all ranks of society in the town, are to be found in a heightened form in the behavior of members of the official class. The first of these is that it is considered impolite to admire too vociferously anything belonging to another. In the case of children or houses, the rationalization is that this will bring catastrophe to the admired object, because such remarks can unwittingly conceal the malice of the evil eye, or tempt God to bring destruction to the owner" (Masters, 1953:210).

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Islam also includes a large body of social legislation..." (Masters, 1953:304).

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs, but not enough information to know with certainty.

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god and non-human supernatural beings are present among the Kurds. However, sufficient ethnographic information on the nature of these beings is not available.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238 indicates that "a high god is present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Limited information is available regarding the nature of God.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Two demands of etiquette, although they may occasionally be observed in all ranks of society in the town, are to be found in a heightened form in the behavior of members of the official class. The first of these is that it is considered impolite to admire too vociferously anything belonging to another. In the case of children or houses, the rationalization is that this will bring catastrophe to the admired object, because such remarks can unwittingly conceal the malice of the evil eye, or tempt God to bring destruction to the owner" (Masters, 1953:210).

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: "Fundamental is the complete separate nature of God and Man, and man's inability to bridge this gap. The whole heterodox gamut from Sufi mystics to essentially shamanistic spirit-medium cults represent attempts at direct communication with God -- at bridging this very un-bridgeable gap. The Kurdish derwish sects occupy a position towards the shamanistic pole of this continuum. Awareness of, or communication with God, is obtained by rhythmic incantations, drumming and rhythmic movements of the body, and self mortification; weeping and seizures are frequent" (Barth, 1953:82).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

— No

Notes: "There does not appear to be much thought about ghosts" (Masters, 1953:315).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

— Yes

Notes: "The people of Rowanduz also believe in jinni (the same noun as in Arabic), spirits who, in contrast, characteristically cause great harm. They are held to be evil spirits who constitute a separate order of creation, like the birds or the animals, and are not necessarily related to mankind. The Kurds also speak of shaytan ('satan,' used in the Quran and the Arabic derivation of the Hebrew word for 'adversary'), devilish beings like the jinni, but of a more congenial and ingenious character than the jinni" (Masters, 1953:315).

Belief in afterlife:

— I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information regarding beliefs about the afterlife

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

— I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

— I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information. Masters, 1953:210 is suggestive of supernatural punishment, but there is not enough information to make a firm conclusion.

Reincarnation in this world:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

— Yes

Notes: After the corpse is washed, it is wrapped in a white sheet and interred—only the wealthy can afford wooden coffins (Masters, 1953:282). "The grave is prepared by laborers prior to the arrival of the procession, and is so oriented that when the corpse is laid within on its right side, the face will look in the general direction of Mecca, in Rowanduz to the southwest" (Masters, 1953:282).

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of mummification is found in the primary ethnographic source.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

–Yes [specify]: On right side

Notes: "The grave is prepared by laborers prior to the arrival of the procession, and is so oriented that when the corpse is laid within on its right side, the face will look in the general direction of Mecca, in Rowanduz to the southwest" (Masters, 1953:282).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of cannibalism found in the primary ethnographic source.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No evidence for exposure to the elements is found in the primary ethnographic source.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No evidence for feeding corpses to animals is found in the primary ethnographic source.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1950 (Secondary Bone/Body Treatment) indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of grave goods is found in the principal ethnographic sources.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below and Masters, 1953, page 282 for more details on formal burials.

In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "A procession now takes place, leading from the house of the deceased to the mosque and then to the cemetery" (Masters, 1953:282).

Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of domestic burials is found in the principal ethnographic source.

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information regarding beliefs about the afterlife

Belief in afterlife:

– I don't know

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– Field doesn't know

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Notes: After the corpse is washed, it is wrapped in a white sheet and interred-only the wealthy can afford wooden coffins (Masters, 1953:282). "The grave is prepared by laborers prior to the arrival of the procession, and is so oriented that when the corpse is laid within on its right side, the face will look in the general direction of Mecca, in Rowanduz to the southwest" (Masters, 1953:282).

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Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme high god and non-human supernatural beings are present among the Kurds. However, sufficient ethnographic information on the nature of these beings is not available.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

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This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 238 indicates that "a high god is present, active, and specifically supportive of human morality" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Additionally, supporting ethnographic information provides evidence for God as an agent of supernatural punishment (Masters, 1953:210). No further information on the nature of supernatural monitoring is available.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "Two demands of etiquette, although they may occasionally be observed in all ranks of society in the town, are to be found in a heightened form in the behavior of members of the official class. The first of these is that it is considered impolite to admire too vociferously anything belonging to another. In the case of children or houses, the rationalization is that this will bring catastrophe to the admired object, because such remarks can unwittingly conceal the malice of the evil eye, or tempt God to bring destruction to the owner" (Masters, 1953:210).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information. Masters, 1953:210 is suggestive of supernatural punishment, but there is not enough information to make a firm conclusion.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs, but not enough information to know with certainty.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Islam also includes a large body of social legislation..." (Masters, 1953:304).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "Mullas are not bound to celibacy, and the three in Rowanduz were married" (Masters, 1953:298).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: "The ninth lunar month, Ramadan , is that in which absolute fasting is required between sunrise and sunset of every Muslim" (Masters, 1953:306).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: "The use of alcoholic beverages, gambling, and the eating of pork (as well as certain other 'unclean' animals) are specifically prohibited in the Quran" (Masters, 1953:305).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: "Prayer is required five times daily of every Muslim, male or female. The times of prayer come at dawn, a few minutes after noon, a point approximately between noon and nightfall, a few minutes after sunset, and at nightfall. In addition, an extremely pious person may add two prayers during the night" (Masters, 1953:301).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: "An outstanding event for boys between the ages of four and six years is circumcision, which, although not mentioned in the Quran, has come to be an essential attribute of a Muslim. 'You are now a Muslim,' a father in Rowanduz tells a son who has undergone the operation" (Masters, 1953:259).

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "The use of alcoholic beverages, gambling, and the eating of pork (as well as certain other “unclean” animals) are specifically prohibited in the Quran" (Masters, 1953:305).

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "Mullas are not bound to celibacy, and the three in Rowanduz were married" (Masters, 1953:298).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

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Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

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Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

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E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

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Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: "The use of alcoholic beverages, gambling, and the eating of pork (as well as certain other "unclean" animals) are specifically prohibited in the Quran" (Masters, 1953:305).

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: SCCS Variable 237 indicates that the Kurds have 2 levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a larger chiefdom. (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, the Kurds have been integrated into other political systems, and are best described as a part of a larger political unit. "In the 1900s government control penetrated further into the local level, and administrators dealt directly with the leaders of individual tribes and villages. Thus, Kurdish leaders are now found at the local level, and their influence is derived from personal attributes such as generosity, honor, and the ability to persuade and to deal with government officials. Tribal and lineage leadership is inherited, although there may be several contenders within the family, and other families may challenge and take over the position...The Kurds have been much affected by the different national policies and are now engaged in a long-term effort to gain some form of self-rule. Demands range from local autonomy to the formation of a Kurdish nation-state. Political parties and demands, guerrilla forces, and support from foreign governments are all part of modern Kurdish politics (Busby, 1996)."

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: "The mullas are responsible for religious education, because, although Islamic history is a part of the curriculum in the primary and intermediate schools, religion is not formally taught in any other place than the mosque. Some parents prefer this training to that of the government schools" (Masters, 1953:300).

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: "Girls may also attend religious classes of their own in the summer, identical in content with those given the boys" (Masters, 1953:300).

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Taxes are not mandatory, but donations are expected. "In addition to prayer, a Muslim is expected to give away part of his yearly earnings as alms. In the early days of Islam these contributions were of two types, zakat , a fixed proportion of the income, and sadaqat , optional gifts. The zakat have been absorbed into the government system of taxation, and the townspeople of Rowanduz are thus not held liable, outside of their usual taxes, to enforced charity" (Masters, 1953:303).

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "...normally the prevention and detection of crime is the work of the police, and their direction within the qadha [administrative unit] is charged to the qaimmaqam [chief or leader]" (Masters, 1953:35).

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Kurds rely primarily on intensive agriculture with irrigation, with animal husbandry as a secondary source of subsistence. Fishing makes a small contribution to the food source. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Kurds rely primarily on intensive agriculture with irrigation, with animal husbandry as a secondary source of subsistence. Fishing makes a small contribution to the food source. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "The religious phrasaeology of the townspeople is in the Arabic language. All of their prayers, pious

utterances, and, indeed, their expletives are in Arabic, while everyday speech is Kurdish" (Masters, 1953:293). Arabic is used for religious purposes, but is not unique to the Kurds.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The Muslim religious calendar is lunar, dated from the flight of the Prophet from Mecca in 622 A.D., and consists of twelve months" (Masters, 1953:305).

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In Iraq every male must perform two years' military service after reaching the age of 18 years unless deferred for unfitness, pursuit of a higher education, or some other reason. There are four divisional commands to which recruits are sent for training and service, the transmission from Rowanduz being by lorry to Erbil" (Masters, 1953:42).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Taxes are not mandatory, but donations are expected. "In addition to prayer, a Muslim is expected to give away part of his yearly earnings as alms. In the early days of Islam these contributions were of two types, zakat , a fixed proportion of the income, and sadaqat , optional gifts. The zakat have been absorbed into the government system of taxation, and the townspeople of Rowanduz are thus not held liable, outside of their usual taxes, to enforced charity" (Masters, 1953:303).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "By law primary education in Iraq is free and compulsory, but this ideal is some distance from realization. In the Rowanduz district only a small number of children, sons and daughters of ambitious or wealthy people, are able to attend primary school and fewer still go on to secondary education or to college" (Masters, 1953:48).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: (Masters, 1953:48)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Public order is maintained by the qadha [district] -police and minor violations of the civil code (few of the townspeople have recourse to 'tribal law') as well as legal processes are handled directly by the judge" (Masters, 1953:55).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The government uses both the Muslim and the Gregorian systems, and Friday is the weekly holiday" (Masters, 1953:305).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In government schools, students are taught to read and write in Arabic, Kurdish (Masters, 1953:48).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In Iraq every male must perform two years' military service after reaching the age of 18 years unless deferred for unfitness, pursuit of a higher education, or some other reason. There are four divisional commands to which recruits are sent for training and service, the transmission from Rowanduz being by lorry to Erbil" (Masters, 1953:42).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: "It is important to notice that there are two main bodies of criminal law in Iraq, a civil code administered by judges appointed by the Ministry of Justice, and that commonly called 'tribal law,' executed by local administrative officers. There are in the Rowanduz district a number of groups who can have recourse to tribal law, and its administration is not charged to the local judge, but is an added task of the qaimmaqam [chief]. Hence the office of that official in Rowanduz has often the aspect of a courtroom, the qaimmaqam and his clerk patiently and laboriously inquiring into the intricacies of some rural feud through an interminable parade of witnesses--coarsely-dressed kotchir and hillmen from remote villages--sworn in on a cloth-covered Quran for their long-winded depositions" (Masters, 1953:27).

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Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "It is important to notice that there are two main bodies of criminal law in Iraq, a civil code administered by judges appointed by the Ministry of Justice, and that commonly called 'tribal law,' executed by local administrative officers" (Masters, 1953:27).

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "There are, at times, government agents of other departments at work in the district, for example, those of the Directorate-General of Agriculture, but their connections are with Erbil or Baghdad, rather than with Rowanduz itself. Some of the most important of these are the engineers of the department charged with public works, for they utilize local labor in their constructions. In the summer of 1951 one such engineer was engaged in resurfacing the road between Rowanduz and Jiadian, and some fifty men from Rowanduz and the district were employed in this work. There are any number of others, such as repairmen for the telephone and telegraph lines, who frequent the area" (Masters, 1953:54).

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The religious law of Islam (Masters, 1953:228).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The execution of the law belongs to the government, either the civil code of the judge or the tribal code of the qaimmaqam [district leader]" (Masters, 1953:189).

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: SCCS Variable 237 indicates that the Kurds have 2 levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of a larger chiefdom. (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). However, the Kurds have been integrated into other political systems, and are best described as a part of a larger political unit. "In the 1900s government control penetrated further into the local level, and administrators dealt directly with the leaders of individual tribes and villages. Thus, Kurdish leaders are now found at the local level, and their influence is derived from personal attributes such as generosity, honor, and the ability to persuade and to deal with government officials. Tribal and lineage leadership is inherited, although there may be several contenders within the family, and other families may challenge and take over the position...The Kurds have been much affected by the different national policies and are now engaged in a long-term effort to gain some form of self-rule. Demands range from local autonomy to the formation of a Kurdish nation-state. Political parties and demands, guerrilla forces, and support from foreign governments are

all part of modern Kurdish politics (Busby, 1996)."

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: "The mullas are responsible for religious education, because, although Islamic history is a part of the curriculum in the primary and intermediate schools, religion is not formally taught in any other place than the mosque. Some parents prefer this training to that of the government schools" (Masters, 1953:300).

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Notes: "By law primary education in Iraq is free and compulsory, but this ideal is some distance from realization. In the Rowanduz district only a small number of children, sons and daughters of ambitious or wealthy people, are able to attend primary school and fewer still go on to secondary education or to college" (Masters, 1953:48).

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: (Masters, 1953:48)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Taxes are not mandatory, but donations are expected. "In addition to prayer, a Muslim is expected to give away part of his yearly earnings as alms. In the early days of Islam these contributions were of two types, zakat , a fixed proportion of the income, and sadaqat , optional gifts. The zakat have been absorbed into the government system of taxation, and the townspeople of Rowanduz are thus not held liable, outside of their usual taxes, to enforced charity" (Masters, 1953:303).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "...normally the prevention and detection of crime is the work of the police, and their direction within the qadha [administrative unit] is charged to the qaimmaqam [chief or leader]" (Masters, 1953:35).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Notes: "Public order is maintained by the qadha [district] -police and minor violations of the civil code (few of the townspeople have recourse to 'tribal law') as well as legal processes are handled directly by the judge" (Masters, 1953:55).

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Notes: "It is important to notice that there are two main bodies of criminal law in Iraq, a civil code administered by judges appointed by the Ministry of Justice, and that commonly called 'tribal law,' executed by local administrative officers" (Masters, 1953:27).

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– Yes

Notes: The religious law of Islam (Masters, 1953:228).

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The execution of the law belongs to the government, either the civil code of the judge or the tribal code of the qaimmaqam [district leader]" (Masters, 1953:189).

Warfare

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "In Iraq every male must perform two years' military service after reaching the age of 18 years unless deferred for unfitness, pursuit of a higher education, or some other reason. There are four

divisional commands to which recruits are sent for training and service, the transmission from Rowanduz being by lorry to Erbil" (Masters, 1953:42).

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

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Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "The religious phrasaeology of the townspeople is in the Arabic language. All of their prayers, pious utterances, and, indeed, their expletives are in Arabic, while everyday speech is Kurdish" (Masters, 1953:293). Arabic is used for religious purposes, but is not unique to the Kurds.

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– Yes

Notes: In government schools, students are taught to read and write in Arabic, Kurdish (Masters, 1953:48).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In government schools, students are taught to read and write in Arabic, Kurdish (Masters, 1953:48).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: "The Muslim religious calendar is lunar, dated from the flight of the Prophet from Mecca in 622 A.D., and consists of twelve months" (Masters, 1953:305).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The government uses both the Muslim and the Gregorian systems, and Friday is the weekly holiday" (Masters, 1953:305).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Kurds rely primarily on intensive agriculture with irrigation, with animal husbandry as a secondary source of subsistence. Fishing makes a small contribution to the food source. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Kurds rely primarily on intensive agriculture with irrigation, with animal husbandry as a secondary source of subsistence. Fishing makes a small contribution to the food source. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.